

Kinetics and Mechanism of Dissociation of Metal Chelates : Part VII. Acid-catalysed Dissociation of Diaquobisacetyl- acetonatochromium(III) ion.

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Manuscript received 12 July 1973; accepted 22 August 1973

The rate of dissociation of diaquobisacetylacetonatochromium(III) ion into tetraaquomonoacetylacetonatochromium(III) ion in aqueous perchloric acid media has been investigated spectrophotometrically. The reaction occurs by two concurrent paths according to the following rate law :

$$\text{Rate} = k' [\text{complex}] + k''_{H^+} [\text{complex}] [H^+]$$

The values of the activation parameters corresponding to k' and k''_{H^+} suggest solvent-assisted dissociation of the complex and its conjugate acid for the two paths respectively as in the case of the dissociation of trisacetylacetonatochromium(III) reported earlier.

DURING spectral studies¹ it was observed that $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ undergoes stepwise dissociation through the formation of the intermediates $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$. As an extension of the earlier work on the dissociation of trisacetylacetonatochromium(III) to the corresponding bis-complex, the dissociation of the diaquobisacetylacetonatochromium(III) ion to the monoacetylacetonato complex has been studied as reported below.

Experimental

A pure solution of $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ was prepared as follows : $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ (20 g) was refluxed on a waterbath with 0.005M HClO_4 (600 ml) with frequent shaking till the pH of the solution rose to about 4 indicating that most of the acid was consumed. Requisite quantity of fairly strong HClO_4 was added to the reaction mixture to make it 0.005M in free HClO_4 and the entire set of operations was repeated till almost all the $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ was dissolved. The solution was then cooled, filtered to remove unreacted $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ and the filtrate was then extracted with purified ether to remove the last traces of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ and free acetylacetonone from the solution. The aqueous phase contained $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ and the purity of the solution was checked by analysis. Chromium was estimated volumetrically after oxidation to Cr(VI) by bromate in acid medium and acetylacetonone volumetrically by treatment with Ce(IV) perchlorate² (Found : Cr, 82.57 mM; acetylacetonone, 165.2 mM). The concentration of free HClO_4 in the solution was determined by estimating total perchlorate ion by ion-exchange salt-splitting method using cation exchanger (Dowex 50W-X8)

in H^+ form and subtracting therefrom the ClO_4^- equivalent to chromium.

All other reagents used were of reagent quality or else purified by suitable methods. Distilled water redistilled in all-glass still was used for making all the solutions.

The rate of acid-catalysed dissociation was measured spectrophotometrically at 560 nm which corresponds to an absorption maximum of both the reacting complex $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ (ϵ_M^{560} , 34) and the product $[\text{Cr}(\text{acac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ (ϵ_M^{560} , 25.0) (see Fig. 1). The experimental solution was 0.005M in the complex and a 4 cm cell was used to have sufficient change in absorbance with time during the progress of the reaction.

The rates of reactions were studied under various conditions (acid concentration, temperature and ionic strength) using a sample quenching technique³. The pseudo-first-order rate constants were evaluated graphically by plotting $\log (A_0 - A_\infty)/(A_t - A_\infty)$ vs. time (t) in the usual way using for A_∞ the value expected for the quantitative formation of the mono-complex. The spectrum of the mono-complex (Fig. 1B) was obtained on the solutions of bis-complex in various acid concentrations (0.1-0.5M) after being kept at 80° for sufficiently long period (ca 18 hr) after which the spectrum, which was distinctly different from that of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ (see Fig. 1), remained unchanged on further aging indicating complete dissociation.

Results and Discussions

For the evaluation of rate constants under different experimental conditions, the reaction was followed well over 40% and in several cases even upto 80-90%

of the total change in absorbance expected for the complete transformation of the bis- to the mono-complex. In this entire range the observed linearity of the pseudo-first-order plots were a satisfactory indication that there was no complication due to any reverse or consecutive reaction.

The pseudo-first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , have been found to vary with the concentration of H^+ ion (see Fig. 2) in a manner which suggests that the

dissociation of diaquobisacetylacetonatochromium(III) ion in acid media proceeds in accordance with the following rate law :

$$\text{Rate} = k'[\text{complex}] + k''H^+[\text{complex}][H^+] \quad \dots (1)$$

Hence,

$$k_{obs} = k' + k''H^+[H^+] \quad \dots (2)$$

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of
 (A) $Cr(acac)_2(H_2O)_2^{2+}$, 0.005M,
 (B) $Cr(acac)(H_2O)_4^{2+}$, 0.005M,
 (C) $Cr(H_2O)_6^{3+}$, 0.005M,
 in aqueous perchloric acid.

Fig. 2. Dependence of rate constant, k_{obs} , on perchloric acid concentration.

possibly solvent-assisted dissociations involving a molecule of water which is hydrogen bonded to the ligand :

tion, however, leads to a loss in aromaticity with a consequent greater lability as in the case of the non-protonated complex mentioned above.

where, ORO stands for acac or acacH as the case may be.

The Cr(acac) chelate ring is exceptionally stable and rather inert due to quasiaromatic character⁵. But rupture of one of the metal-chelate bond leads to an open structure of much greater lability due to loss of aromaticity. This supports the suggestion that the second step in the change represented by equation (3) is very much faster than the first one. Protonation of the chelated ligand may not lead to a loss in aromaticity due to the following tautomeric forms :

But strong covalent bonding between the ligand O-atom and H⁺ ion in each of the tautomeric forms will evidently lead to electron withdrawal from the Cr-O bond and thus accounting for a greater lability for the fission of the bond as is indicated by the higher rate for the acid dependent path. Dissociation of this protonated complex (CA) forming the intermediate having one -acacH with unidentate func-

tion of electrons from the aqua ligand compared to that from the ligand being replaced.

As in the case of Cr(acac)₃ the relative rates for both the acid independent and acid dependent paths are primarily entropy controlled since the faster acid dependent path has the higher ΔH[‡] value. The higher value is evidently due to the contribution of ΔH for the protonation pre-equilibrium (Equation (4a) to the observed ΔH[‡] value for k''_{H⁺} (= k''·K_{H⁺}). It is also noted that the value of k''_{H⁺}/k' for Cr(acac)₂(H₂O)₂⁺ is much less than the corresponding value of Cr(acac)₃. This may partly be due to K_{H⁺} for the Cr(acac)₂(H₂O)₂⁺ being less than that of the tris-complex since addition of a proton to the unchanged substrate Cr(acac)₃ should be more favourable than to one having a positive charge Cr(acac)₂(H₂O)₂⁺.

The effect of ionic strength (μ) on the rate constants k' and k''_{H⁺} has also been studied and it is seen from the data given in Table 1 (see Fig. 2) that under otherwise identical conditions a decrease in μ decreases k''_{H⁺} without, however, affecting k' as is expected on the basis of the assigned mechanisms.

TABLE 2
Path corresponding to

Complex	k'		k'' _{H⁺}		Ref.
	ΔH [‡]	ΔS [‡]	ΔH [‡]	ΔS [‡]	
	kcal/mole	e.u.	kcal/mole	e.u.	
Cr(ox) ₃ ³⁻	—	—	21.6	- 8.4	4
cis-Cr(ox) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ ⁻	—	—	23.9	- 4.5	6
Cr(BigH) ₃ ³⁺	—	—	10.1	-30.2	7
Cr(BigH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ ³⁺	—	—	17.5	< 20.6	7
Cr(PhBigH) ₃ ³⁺	—	—	14.7	-17.6	7
Cr(PhBigH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ ³⁺	—	—	21.6	- 7.8	7
Cr(acac) ₃	13.8	-37.3	20.2	- 14.2	1
Cr(acac) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ ⁺	19.3	-25.1	26.4	- 2.6	Present work

A similar behaviour has been reported¹ in the case of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$.

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